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Professional careers in basic VET: an approach from the students' interests

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Abstract

The main aim of this paper is to present the perspective that the students of basic VET in Valencia (Spain) have about their own professional careers, taking into consideration the different interests that they have in the training they are attending. In order to achieve it, we will focus on the students' perspective through three variables: The reasons for the choice of the program; the expectations they project of their training; and the personal identity, which is understood here as the adjustment between their personal characteristics and the profession for which they are being trained. Overall, the results may provide us with information on the development of basic VET considering the adjustment between interests of the students and the educational offering available, and the meaning the students give to the programs in their professional career started in these educational contexts.

Keywords

vocational education; career development; students' interests; vocational interests

1 Researching professional careers in basic VET

This aim is framed in the research project "Success and dropout pathways in vocational training educational system levels 1 and 2" in the region of Valencia. This project in which three Universities from three Spanish regions participate (Universitat de les Illes Balears, Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona and Universitat de València) has as its main objectives knowing the VET students and the conditions that facilitate their itineraries in this training. Moreover, the research aims to develop proposals in order to reduce early school leaving. All this is conducted through a longitudinal study of the itineraries of the students of VET level 1 (basic VET, FPB) and level 2 (Intermediate-Level Training Cycles, CFGM). This longitudinal approach is essential in the research on students' pathways and transitions, as it permits a better understanding of those processes that the students perform in the educational institution (Casal, Merino & García, 2011). Furthermore, it should also be noted that this is the first time that this methodological approach is used for researching VET in the Valencian Region.

Specifically, in this proposal we will present an analysis focused on the Initial VET (level 1) and aimed at knowing the professional careers projected by the students who attend the programs. In order to develop this analysis, we will focus on the perspective of the students through three variables. Firstly, we analyse the reasons for the choice of the program; secondly, we focus on the expectations they project of their training; and finally, we consider the personal identity, which is understood here as the adjustment between their personal charac-

teristics and the profession for which they are being trained. We consider that these three variables allow us to approach the professional career initiated by the students in basic VET. In this regard, in our analyses about professional careers we start with the definition of pedagogical identity proposed by Basil Bernstein (2000, p.66): “a pedagogic identity is the result of embedding a career in a collective base. The career of a student is a knowledge career, a moral career and a locational career”.

In the analysis presented in this paper we will cross these variables with the professional branches of the programs. We consider that this may allow us to obtain a more exhaustive image of the different professional careers projected by the students of the initial level of VET in the frame of the educational offerings available in the Valencian region. Therefore, it will enable us to assess, on the one hand, the management and development of basic VET in terms of educational policy. On the other hand, we will be able to describe in which programs (and in which professional branches) the students are more or less interested in the content. Moreover, we will describe which students project to a greater or lesser extent a career in the profession in which they are being trained.

The data on which these analyses are based correspond to the results of the first pass of the longitudinal study conducted in the academic course 2016-17. In basic VET, this included a total sample of 737 students distributed in 71 classes of 41 different educational organizations. In the design of the project and definition of the sample we followed a stratified sampling based on three criteria for stratification by clusters: the professional family of the program, the geographical distribution (differentiating between organizations located in the metropolitan area of those who are located outside) and the ownership of the organization. Together, we have a representative sample of basic VET in the Valencian region.

2 Branches and professional expectations

In order to develop this point we have focused on the professional expectations sorted by the different branches studied. For the purpose of the general study, professional expectations are a part of the career development along with professional identity.

We present the results for 4 different items directly related to professional expectations and 2 for professional identity. Every item is studied for the 16 branches studied in this research. Of the 737 students surveyed, we may count with 729 answers to follow the next results.

The 4 items concerning expectations are:

- 8.a - Thanks to the studies I'm following I will be able to have a job which will provide me enough money to live
- 8.b - Thanks to the studies I'm following I think I will manage to pursue what I want
- 8.c - The studies I'm following will help me to have success in my professional career
- 8.d - I will need further training in order to achieve what I really want

The 2 items concerning professional identity are:

- 8.e - The studies I do are adequate to my personal characteristics
- 8.f - I like the profession I'm being trained for

As a general result we may conclude that the most of the students (in almost every case) more than 75% of the sample agree or strongly agree with the statements above indicated. For instance, and 82% of students of the Administration and management branch agree with those statement, as well as the 89% of the Transport and vehicle maintenance.

Table 1 Branches and professional expectations

	8.a	8.b	8.c	8.d
Administration and management	82%	64 %	86%	93%
Agriculture	88%	70 %	82%	92%
Graphic arts	89%	89 %	89%	78%
Crafts	63%	38 %	75%	88%
Trade and marketing	85%	71 %	79%	92%
Electricity and electronic	84%	70 %	86%	84%
Construction and civil work	55%	70 %	63%	82%
Metal working	82%	71 %	82%	84%
Hospitality and turism	85%	67 %	74%	90%
Information and com. Technologies	77%	74 %	81%	90%
Installation and maintenance	83%	60 %	80%	80%
Personal image	86%	81 %	76%	86%
Food industry	78%	67 %	78%	88%
Wood, furniture and cork	86%	71 %	86%	100%
Textile, clothing industry and leather	43%	50 %	71%	100%
Transport and vehicles maintenance	89%	96 %	83%	79%
Total	82%	71 %	82%	89%

In the case of the items referred to the professional identity, percentages of adherence are as follow:

Table 2 Branches and professional identity

	8.e	8.f
Administration and management	70%	65%
Agriculture	78%	88%
Graphic arts	89%	89%
Crafts	50%	63%
Trade and marketing	75%	79%
Electricity and electronic	72%	75%
Construction and civil work	64%	64%
Metal working	76%	81%
Hospitality and tourism	72%	87%
Information and com. Technologies	77%	83%
Installation and maintenance	80%	60%

Personal image	81%	81%
Food industry	67%	89%
Wood, furniture and cork	86%	86%
Textile, clothing industry and leather	57%	50%
Transport and vehicles maintenance	96%	96%
Total	75%	78%

3 Branches and reasons for choice

The items used to study the reasons of choice match perfectly with the answers provided in the expectations items. The list of items used to study this dimension is (I choose to study this program...):

- 9.a Because I like it
- 9.b Because I couldn't enter another one
- 9.c Because there are job opportunities in the field
- 9.d To improve my employability
- 9.e Because my friends are following them
- 9.f Because my career adviser recommended it
- 9.g Because my family wanted e to follow it
- 9.h because it was required by my enterprise
- 9.i Because I couldn't find a job

Table 3 Branches and reasons of choice

	9.a	9.b	9.c	9.d	9.e	9.f	9.g	9.h	9.i
Administration and management	60%	33%	46%	32%	27%	60%	31%	4%	5%
Agriculture	73%	34%	59%	73%	24%	40%	26%	19%	19%
Graphic arts	78%	37%	38%	88%	25%	67%	38%	13%	13%
Crafts	38%	75%	25%	88%	63%	88%	13%	25%	0%
Trade and marketing	70%	55%	49%	67%	22%	48%	27%	25%	15%
Electricity and electronic	74%	37%	53%	74%	29%	43%	31%	5%	18%
Construction and civil work	45%	45%	27%	55%	36%	55%	36%	55%	25%
Metal working	15%	42%	56%	67%	34%	42%	45%	18%	26%
Hospitality and turism	82%	30%	65%	76%	22%	61%	26%	18%	14%
Information and com. Technologies	79%	32%	45%	69%	25%	48%	23%	6%	7%
Installation and maintenance	50%	17%	0%	67%	0%	0%	27%	0%	60%
Personal image	81%	20%	45%	67%	14%	38%	5%	0%	11%
Food industry	67%	44%	33%	56%	33%	33%	38%	0%	0%
Wood, furniture and cork	86%	42%	29%	29%	14%	43%	43%	14%	0%
Textile, clothing industry and leather	38%	62%	25%	29%	13%	63%	38%	13%	13%
Transport and vehicles maintenance	92%	15%	52%	81%	28%	42%	28%	13%	22%
Total	72%	32%	48%	68%	26%	50%	28%	9%	12%

4 Brief conclusions for discussion

Overall, the results may provide us with information on various aspects of the development of basic VET in Valencia: firstly, we may know the adjustment between interests of the students and the educational offering available in this level. Secondly, they may enable us to assess the

meaning the students give to the programs in their training and in the professional career started in these educational contexts. In this way, we may talk about professional careers from the perspective of the students themselves. Thus, we try to relate the student as an actor of his/her own educational biography with the VET system itself and the programs available in a specific territory.

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Biographical notes

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